

STABILITY OF VITAMIN-A IN SESAME OIL

BY S. SEN-GUPTA

Vitamin A in vitaminised sesame oil is rapidly destroyed.

While investigating on the extraction of vitamin-A from fishliver oils, recourse was taken to various vegetable oils such as groundnut, sesame oil etc. By this process the vitamin-A is transferred from the liver oil to the vegetable oils. But the oil should be such as to retain the vitamin for a long time and as such should be examined for its retentive capacity. The stability of vitamin-A in arachis oil and olive oil has been studied by Basu (*Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1941, 1, 165, cf. also Basu and Sen-Gupta, *Curr. Sci.*, 1941, 10, 288). But as sesame oil was also used in the above work, an investigation was undertaken to ascertain the keeping properties of vitamin-A in sesame oil. A variety of sesame oil from the market was analysed for its acid, peroxide and iodine values. Acid value, 10; peroxide value, 7 (expressed in terms of c.c. of 0.002 *N*-thiosulphate); iodine value, 107.

As the oil contained a large amount of free acid it was purified in the usual way *i.e.* by means of a solution of sodium carbonate as follows:

The oil was treated with sufficient amount (as determined by the acid value of the sample under consideration) of a concentrated solution of sodium carbonate to neutralise the free acid present. The soap formed was removed first by filtration and finally by extraction with alcohol (95%). The oil was then dried over sodium sulphate and heated to 150° in an oil-bath for half an hour under vacuum to remove the last traces of moisture.

The oil thus purified was found to have the following characteristics: Acid value, 0.5; peroxide value, 6.0. Thus it was noticed that the treatment did not help in lowering the peroxide value of the original oil to any appreciable extent. This was, however, taken for the study on the stability of vitamin-A.

The oil was mixed with a known concentrate of vitamin-A in such a way that the finished product contained approximately 1000 I.U. of vitamin-A per g., and the potency was measured in terms of Carr-Price blue value which was found to be 10.2. The vitaminised oil thus obtained, was subjected to aeration in a glass bottle closed with a velvet cork with two borings for inlet and outlet tubes. Air previously purified by passing through concentrated sulphuric acid and soda lime was bubbled through the oil placed in the bottle at room temperature. Vitamin-A concentrate was determined by the Carr-Price method. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Period of aeration.	Blue value.	Peroxide value.	Acid value.
0 hrs.	10.2	6.0	0.5
10	9.4	8.5	0.5
20	8.3	11.0	0.5
36	Trace	50.0	0.6

It may be noticed from the table that the vitamin present in the oil was gradually being destroyed and after aeration for 36 hours, no trace of it was noticed as measured

by C.P. blue value method. With the aeration the peroxide value has also increased from 6 to 50 whereas there is no appreciable increase in its acid value. It may be mentioned here that the iodine value of sesame oil is nearer to that of arachis oil whose iodine value generally varies from 85 to 99. But the rate of formation of peroxide in the former case is considerably enhanced and consequently the destruction of vitamin-A in this oil is much rapid when compared to similar destruction of vitamin-A concentrate dissolved in arachis oil as noted by Basu (*loc. cit.*) and Basu and Sen-Gupta (*loc. cit.*). For such rapid destruction of vitamin no other experiment was conducted after incorporation of any suitable antioxidant. It may be noted that the use of antioxidants would retard the peroxide formation as also the rate of destruction of vitamin-A, but since it is obvious from the observations made in this laboratory that in sesame oil peroxide formation is much faster than in arachis oil which is also easily available, it was not considered to be of any practical value to try the effect of antioxidants for this work.

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STUDIES IN FRIES MIGRATION. PART II. THE FRIES MIGRATION OF ESTERS OF 7-HYDROXY-3-ALKYL-4-METHYL-6-ETHYLCOUMARINS

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The Fries rearrangement of the esters of 7-hydroxy-3-alkyl-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarins has been studied. It is observed that the alkyl groups exert but little influence on the course of the migration. The migration products have been subjected to Kostanecki acetylation and various coumarino- α - or γ -pyrones are formed.

In continuation of our work described in the previous part of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 199) we have investigated the Fries rearrangement of different esters of 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethyl- as well as of 7-hydroxy-3-alkyl-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarins. The results obtained confirm our previous conclusions that (1) below a certain temperature the migration does not take place: and, if the migration is carried out at higher temperature, the product gets charred (*cf.* Tarbell and Fanta, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2169); (2) different acyl groups require different temperatures for migration, which vary according to the nature and size of the acyl group, *e.g.*, benzoyl group requires a higher temperature for migration than the acetyl (Rosenmund and Schmurr, *Annalen*, 1928, 460, 56; Baltzly and Bass, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 4292) and (3) the use of aluminium chloride in proportions higher than three moles leads to the contamination of the resulting products with impurities.

In all cases, the migration was smooth and the different substituents present in the coumarin nucleus had little inhibitory influence on the course of the rearrangement. In all cases, the product obtained was found to be 7-hydroxy-3-alkyl-4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetyl- or 8-benzoyl-coumarin, since (i) it gave strong colouration with alcoholic ferric